

Riverbank Erosion Assessment of Sandha River and Identification the Human Induced Key Factor by Using GIS and Remote Sensing Method.

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Abstract: Riverbank erosion is a common natural disaster in Bangladesh. Bangladesh located in the world's largest active Ganges delta where Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna (G-B-M) river systems carry out enormous sediment load simultaneously extensive riverbank erosion is prominent to balance river dynamics. Somewhere this equilibrium could be disturbed by human activities and leads to bank consumption. This study is on riverbank erosion assessment of Sandha River at Rahmatpur and Dehergati unions in Babuganj upazila, as well as detection of probable key factor to bank consumption caused by local human activities. Rapid establishment of a large number of unplanned brickfields along the riverside at the study area requires a huge amount of sediment as raw material, which are extracting from the river bed, point bars, flood plain and other riverine places. This excessive sediment mining alters the local river morphology and imbalance the river dynamics over there. This study was carried out by conducting a questionnaire survey to collect primary data. Remote Sensing (RS) method was used to collect and analyze satellite images. Geographic Information System (GIS) was applied to prepare different models, maps and tables in the study area. In addition, Surfer software was also used to create contour maps and elevation profiles of the study area. These models, maps and tables are showing the sharp changes of the river banks as well as increasing number of brickfields at the study area since 2011. This unusual fluvial sediment excavation for commercial purposes from the riverside should be stopped immediately by effective surveillance of related authority along with proper distribution of accreted land among the affected local people is essential.

1. Introduction:

Riverbank erosion is a common natural calamity in Bangladesh. Geographical location as well as sediment characteristics made Bangladesh vulnerable to extreme riverbank erosion (Hasan et al., 2018). This riverbank erosion has become severe in recent few years in Barishal because of human activities accelerating this acute bank consumption. The local people are entirely depended on river and river is considered as a resource to them. There are some man made causes that facilitate bank erosion, among these excessive sediment mining from adjacent to the riverbank, bars, flood plain and river bed could be a major factor to bank consumption and lateral river migration at study area (Erskine, 1990). Sediment removal from the channel and bar skimming deepen the channel as well as increasing the channel slop that ultimately trigger bank

erosion (Clements, 2018). Rivers have an inherent dynamic balance between some physical factors: such as flow of river, channel depth, width, slop, particle size and amount of sediment supply, either erosion or deposition will promote if the equilibrium between the factors is changed (Langbein & Leopold, 1970). River morphology could be changed because of excessive sediment mining or insufficient sediment supply (Clements, 2018). In the study area, riverside sediment is being extracted commercially and using as raw material at brickfields. There are more than 17 brickfields have established in just 4 kilometers in the study area along the Sandha river within last 9 years. Primary and secondary data of the study area show that, the river bank erosion has been increasing since 2011. More than 250 families became homeless, school, madrasah, local market along with mosques and croplands have gone into the Sandha River. Nearby Barishal airport and Dhaka-Barishal Highway is now under risk due to the horrible bank erosion. This study includes primary and secondary data. By conducting a questionnaire survey at study area, primary data was collected. Secondary data was collected from satellite images, journal papers, scientific articles, newspapers, books and websites. Primary and secondary data evaluation shows that, lateral river migration due to riverbank erosion together with human disturbance has changed the local river morphology. The primary objectives of this study are to find out the feasible man-made prime factor and to assess the amount of total eroded and deposited land at the study area.

2. Materials and Methodology:

2.1 Study Area:

This study was conducted at Rahmatpur and Dehergati unions alongside of Sandha River, in Babuganj subdistrict, Barishal. Sandha River originates from Arial Khan River near Muladi and falls to Kacha River near Pirojpur. The study area falls between 22°46’50” and 22°51’10” north latitudes and between 90°15’40” and 90°21’0” east longitude. Plain topography is prominent in the study area, the sediment characteristics is almost similar with other fluvial deposits in Barishal region. Medium to fine grained sand with a few amount of coarse to fine grained silt and clay(Hasan et al., 2018). The riverside sediments are loosely compacted with high moisture content. The area is highly influenced by semi- diurnal tide.

Figure 01: Location map of study area. Light red colored area depicts the selected Rahmatpur and Dehergati unions and red colored triangle marker indicates the study points.

2.2 Data:

A questionnaire survey was conducted at study area. Total 36 data were collected from the local people, who are suffered due to bank erosion either directly or indirectly. Local people individually expressed their opinion about the human generated potential key factor that accelerating the terrible riverbank erosion at the study area.

Secondary data was collected from different sources, such as: satellite images, scientific journals, articles, newspapers, scientific magazines, textbooks and web portals. The Landsat 4-5 TM C1 Level-1 images of 2011 and Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1 Level-1 images of 2020 were collected from USGS Earth Explorer website. Time series data from 2011 to 2020 were collected from Google Earth pro software.

2.3 Methods:

2.3.1 Questionnaire Survey:

The primary data collected by a questionnaire survey were processed as well as analyzed by using Microsoft Excel software. A convenient graphical pie chart was prepared to illustrate the feasible man-made key factors to erosion at the study area as well as a field study was carried out to monitor the human activities along the river.

Table 01: Primary data summary based on the questionnaire survey conducted in the study area

Name of Study Area (Union)	Total Affected Households	Total Data	Total Brickfields in 2011	Total Brickfields in 2020	Total Vulnerable Points
Rahmatpur	180	21	5	16	4
Dehergati	70	15	2	8	4

2.3.2 Elevation profiles:

To make the elevation profiles of the vulnerable points of the study area, Surfer 13, Google Earth Pro, TCX converter, Microsoft excel software were used. Firstly the KML files of geographic coordinates of the selected points were collected from Google Earth pro and then converted to CSV, GPX and excel format respectively by using TCX, GPS visualizer and Microsoft excel. Altitude values were added from GPS visualizer. Then the CSV data were imported into Surfer 13 software. At first CSV files were converted into Grid files. Further Grid files plotted into the layer to make contour and elevation profile maps. Elevation profiles delineate the comparative changes of river cross-section.

2.3.3 Normalize Difference Water Index (NDWI):

Landsat 4-5 TM C1 Level-1 images in TIF format, dated April, 2011, band number 2 and 4. Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1 Level-1 images of similar format, from April, 2020 and band number 3 and 4 were picked up and processed by GIS 10.4.1 software. To differentiate the waterbodies, vegetation and uncovered land, NDWI is used. The following formula is used to make NDWI map:

$$NDWI = \frac{GREEN - NIR}{GREEN + NIR}$$

Waterbody features have higher reflectance of NIR band than G band, so waterbodies show positive values, on the other hand vegetation features have negative values due to lower reflectance of NIR band than G band, that's why vegetation features show negative values. The value ranges of NDVI from -1 to +1 (McFEETERS, 1996).

2.3.4 Erosion, Accretion and Channel Migration:

Total eroded and deposited lands were calculated by drawing path lines and polygons into the satellite map of Google Earth pro. Two Images of December, 2011 and March, 2020 were used to illustrate the total eroded and deposited land, then the total consumed and accreted lands were calculated separately by using measurement tools of Google Earth pro. Landsat 4-5 TM C1 Level-1 image of 2011, Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1 Level-1 image of 2020 and GIS software were used to make a channel migration map, and an erosion accretion map. Path lines were drawn along north and south bank of the Sandha River in satellite maps of two different time periods. The deviation between two lines at the similar bankside was filled by polygons. To differentiate the eroded and deposited lands, red and green colors were used.

2.3.5 Satellite Images Analysis:

Satellite images of December, 2011 and March, 2020 were extracted from Google Earth pro to visualize the brickfields in two different times in the study area and made some comparative maps.

2.3.6 Land Use Land Cover (LULC) Method:

Land Use Land Cover (LULC) is a supervised image classification method. For quantitative analysis of satellite image, supervised classification is the most frequently used process (Rwanga & Ndambuki, 2017). Land Use/Land Cover maps of two different time periods were made by GIS 10.4.1 software. LULC map depicts the different land cover features of the study area such as natural waterbodies, vegetation, uncovered land, artificial surface and transitions of land cover due to human activities. Landsat 4-5 TM C1 Level-1 images packages of 2011 and Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1 Level-1 images packages of 2020 were extracted. 1 to 7 bands were used for each LULC map. Raster processing of composite bands, masking in spatial analyst tools, parametric maximum likelihood image classifier were executed to conduct this image classification method. 2, 4 and 7 bands were selected for Landsat 4-5 TM C1 Level-1 image. 2, 3 and 4 bands were selected for Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1 Level-1 image.

After completing the LULC map, the accuracy assessment has done for each LULC map. User's accuracy, Producer's accuracy, Overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient assessment were measured through matrix by using user classification and reference image. Between reality and model prediction, Kappa can be used as a measure of agreement (Tilahun, 2015). User's accuracy, Producer's accuracy, Overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient were calculated by using following formulas:

$$\text{User's Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of correctly classified pixels in each category}}{\text{Total number of classified pixels in that category (the row total)}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Producer's Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of correctly classified pixels in each category}}{\text{Total number of reference pixels in that category (the column total)}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Overall Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Total Number of correctly classified pixels (diagonal)}}{\text{Total number of reference pixels}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Kappa coefficient} = \frac{(TS \times TCS) - \sum(\text{column total} \times \text{row total})}{TS^2 - \sum(\text{column total} \times \text{row total})} \times 100$$

3. Result and Discussions:

The questionnaire survey shows, at about 67% people believe that excessive sediment mining for commercial purposes is the main reason to local riverbank erosion whereas 13% people commented about deforestation. Besides 11% and 9% local people opined that, boat induced hydraulic waves and poor navigability due to river mismanagement are the feasible key factor for local bank consumption (figure, 02).

Figure 02: Feasible man-made factors based on questionnaire survey

Figure 03, shows the comparative morphological changes of Sandha River at selected study points. The study point's areas are occupied by red colored rectangle and circle respectively. Maps (a) and (b) of figure 03 show the acute bank erosion at the south bank of Rahmatpur study point where the cut bank of meander is vulnerable due to extreme hydraulic action.

The river at Rahmatpur study point was prominently narrow as well as the point bar area was elaborated. But, the point bar area was evidently lower at Dehergati study point in 2011.

In 2020, the river has been widened immensely at Rahmatpur study point but not prominently expanding at Dehergati study point. Comparison map shows the point bar side and cut bank of meander at Rahmatpur study point move away from each other indicating relatively poor sedimentation at the north bank bar point opposite of Rahmatpur section but at Dehergati section, there are plentiful sediment has accreted. The river breadth has been increased slightly at Dehergati study point.

Figure 03: Comparison maps between 2011 and 2020 satellite images of Rahmatpur (a) and Dehergati (b) study points shows the morphological changes of Sandha River.

Figure 04, illustrating the lateral migration of channel at Rahmatpur and Dehergati unions since 2011. In 2020, river channel has been widened extensively at meanders that indicate acute river bank erosion at the adjoining places of meanders. Overall channel width has been increasing over last nine years.

Figure 04: Lateral migration of Sandha River bank lines over last nine years. Green and red lines are representing bank lines of Sandha River in 2011 and 2020 respectively.

Figure 5, indicating Sandha is a sharp dynamic river due to morphological instability. The map showing extensive erosion has occurred along both north and south bank at study area, whereas total erosion along north bank is about 291 acres and deposition is about 78.66 acres, in last nine years the rate of erosion and accretion along north bank are 32.33acres/year and 8.74 acres/year.

On the other hand total erosion along south bank is about 56.47 acres and total deposition at about 144.81 acres. The erosion and accretion rate along south bank are 6.24 acres/year and

16.09 acres/year respectively in recent nine years. It is clear from the figure 5, north bank of the river has been suffering acute riverbank erosion and relatively higher deposition along the south bank. Since 2011, total land consumption and deposition in study area is about 347.47 acres and 223.47 acres respectively. Net erosion is approximately 124 acres in last nine years. The erosion and accretion data have presented in a table given below

Table 02: Erosion and accretion data of study area.

Time Period (year)	Location Rahmatpur & Dehergati (Sandha River)	Erosion		Accretion	
		Total (acres)	Rate (acres/year)	Total (acres)	Rate (acres/year)
2011-2020	North bank	291	32.33	78.66	8.74
	South bank	56.47	6.27	144.81	16.09
	Total reach	347.47	38.61	223.47	24.83
	Net erosion (acres)	124			

Figure 05: Erosion & Accretion map delineating the places and total amount of land consumption and deposition at study area.

Figure 06, is showing the relative changes of the river morphology. Elevation profile indicates the channel cross-section of red circle area. In 2011, bank slopes of Sandha river at Rahmatpur section, were steeper than in 2020. Specifically at the right hand slopes. The cross-section area at Rahmatpur has increased and the bank slope has decreased in last 9 years.

These changes are indicating severe bank erosion along right side slope or south bank at Rahmatpur study point. Changing color in contour maps also indicate the changes of surface pattern in study area.

Figure 06: Comparative elevation profile maps between (a) and (b) in 2011 and 2020 indicate the relative changes of cross-section of Sandha River at Rahmatpur study point.

There are similar cases at Dehergati study point where the channel cross-section has widened, bank slopes has become more gentle in 2020 than 2011, demonstrating by figure 7. The rising number of color value also indicate the transition of surface cover at the study area.

Figure 07: Comparative elevation profile maps between (a) and (b) in 2011 and 2020 indicate the relative changes of cross-section of Sandha River at Dehergati study point.

Normalize Difference Water Index (NDWI) of 2011 and 2020 in figure 8, indicate the changes of local waterbodies, surface cover and vegetation. Channel width has increased explicitly in 2020, specifically at the menaders where intense riverbank erosion is evident. Vegetation cover has declined abruptly in 2020 in the study area. Decreasing vegetation and increasing uncovered land indicates the alteration of land use over the study area. Riverine land has become uncovered prominently at Dehergati, and at westward side of Rahmatpur study point shown in (b) map of figure 08.

Figure 08: Normalize Difference Water Index (NDWI) maps (a) in 2011 and (b) in 2020 are demonstrating the relative changes of waterbodies, vegetation, and surface cover.

The most prominent factor is in the Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) maps (a) & (b) of two different years are demonstrating the alteration of land pattern along the riverside at Dehergati and Rahmatpur section, where deep brown color occupied area indicates the brickfield zones. In 2011, these deep brown zones were scattered but in 2020, these deep brown zones has increased and integrated (Figure 9). This sharp transition of land use pattern indicates the number of brickfields has been increased and most of the brickfields have established dramatically in recent nine years. LULC maps (a) and (b) are also showing the relative changes of river breadth, amount of vegetation cover and concrete surface by blue, green and grey color respectively.

Figure 09: Land Use Land Cover (LULC) maps (a) in 2011 and (b) in 2020 are showing the relative changes of land use/land cover at Rahmatpur and Dehergati unions.

Table 03: Accuracy measurement of LULC map (a)

Landuse class	Waterbody	Vegetation	Brickfields	Uncovered Land	Concrete Surface	Total User	User's Accuracy
Waterbody	15	0	0	0	3	18	0.8333
Vegetation	0	17	0	2	0	19	0.895
Brickfields	0	0	15	0	0	15	1
Uncovered land	0	0	0	16	1	17	0.941
Concrete surface	0	0	0	0	6	6	1
Total (Producer)	15	17	15	18	10	75	
Producer's Accuracy	1	1	1	0.888	0.6		
Overall Accuracy	0.92						
Kappa Coefficient	0.898						

Table 04: Accuracy measurement of LULC map (b)

Landuse class	Waterbody	Vegetation	Brickfields	Uncovered Land	Concrete Surface	Total User	User's Accuracy
Waterbody	15	0	0	0	0	15	1
Vegetation	0	16	0	2	0	18	0.888
Brickfields	0	0	19	0	0	19	1
Uncovered land	0	1	0	13	0	14	0.928
Concrete surface	0	0	0	0	11	11	1
Total (Producer)	15	17	19	15	11	77	
Producer's Accuracy	1	0.941	1	0.866	1		
Overall Accuracy	0.961						
Kappa Coefficient	0.95						

Figure 10, showing the brickfield number and location in 2011 and 2020 at study area. In 2011, there were only seven brickfields in the study area. But in 2020, the number of brickfield has climbed up rapidly along the riverbank in study area. Currently, there are 24 brickfields at Dehergati and Rahmatpur study points.

Figure 10: Comparison map between (a) in 2011 and (b) in 2020 shows the increasing number of brickfields over study area.

The raw material of these brickfields is fluvial sediments extracted from riverside lands, point bars, flood plains and river bed. This exceeding sediment mining for commercial purposes make the river bank vulnerable to erosion. Dynamic equilibrium between erosion and accretion of the

river has disturbed by excessive riverine sediments mining(Clements, 2018). If sediment removal is higher than sediment input at any location, this results morphological changes locally and leads to riverbank erosion(Langbein & Leopold, 1970). Erosion & accretion Statistic stable shows that, the net erosion of the study area is about 124 acres that means the dynamic balance of Sandha River has hindered by human activities. On the basis of primary and secondary data, it is clear that the excessive sediment mining is the feasible prime factor for riverbank erosion at the study area.

4. Conclusion:

Riverbank erosion is an unavoidable natural event perspective of Bangladesh. Southern part of the country specifically Barishal is vulnerable to erosion because of geographical location, sedimentological characteristics, local geologic settings, river morphology, heavy rainfall and climate change. Along with human activities like excessive sediment extraction, deforestation, poor river management, busy river traffic and unplanned habitation facilitate terrible bank erosion. There is no sustainable rehabilitation for local homeless people who already lost their land due to bank erosion even the accreted land is not being distributed properly to the damaged people. Primary data, elevation profiles, river migration, erosion-accretion maps, satellite images, NDWI and LULC model clearly demonstrating rapid change of local land cover due to establishment of numerous brickfields in recent nine years at the study area which are using the fluvial sediment extracted commercially from the river sides. The removal of huge amount riverine sediment makes imbalance the river dynamics and locally promotes devastating bank erosion. This study can be carried out further by evaluating the local socio economic impacts and long term impacts on local biodiversity as well as river morphology due to bank consumption. In addition, sediment load measurement and grain size analysis could be added in future. This excessive riverine sediment mining and unplanned brickfields establishment should be prohibited by regular surveillance of adhering authority. Government should be taken effective steps for proper rehabilitation and accreted land distribution among the affected and homeless people.

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